

THE ROLE OF THE PHENOMENON OF TOPONEGIZ IN THE EXPLANATION OF THE TERM TOPONEGIZ

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Annotation: In the article, brief information was given about the role of toponymization in the interpretation of the toponymy term in Ishtikhan and Payariq districts of Samarkand region. It is natural that since the beginning of speaking, a person names himself differently from others, names the places he lives in comparison with other places, based on existing linguistic and extralinguistic conditions. "From the very beginning of human society, a person felt the need to give a name to the area where he lives, and from this period, any desired object, starting from the person himself, has its own name.

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Toponyms embody the history of the entire nation, the stable and changing evolution of a specific language. A word or combination chosen as a toponym does not become a toponym by itself, that is, an important historical-linguistic process is observed for the selection of a specific topoobject as a name, and as a result it is selected for a name. The phenomenon of toponymization plays an important role in the creation of a topological object. Because this phenomenon, as an expression of the law of occurrence of most toponyms, reflects the evolutionary stages of the development of languages since ancient times. The importance of the phenomenon of toponymization is that it serves to enrich and complete our knowledge about the historical problems of linguistics through the formation of toponyms indicative of modernity.

As noted, the words chosen to name topological objects do not immediately become toponyms, but go through a certain process under the influence of linguistic and non-linguistic extralinguistic factors related to the language in use. This process is called toponymization[1]. The phenomenon of toponymization is explained as toponymization in the Russian language scientific literature. Several scientists have conducted scientific observations and researches about this. For example, N. Podolskaya drew attention to this phenomenon to prepare a dictionary article in the

dictionary of onomastic terms [1:132]. T. Enazarov touched upon this issue in order to carry out etymological research on toponyms [2]. Things don't become different by themselves. They are distinguished from each other by their names, which summarize their characteristic features. Everyone knows that any name has a set of characteristics that distinguish it from another name or something else. Named objects are considered objects of name(s). Therefore, it is natural for each name to have a named object. It has been noted in nomenclature for a long time that there are names of imaginary things and events as well as the names of concrete things. We know that names for their objects were not formed all at once, but went through stages of formation. It was studied in several stages. This is called the naming process[3]. T. Enazarov studied this case, that is, the process of naming on the example of toponyms, so he called it the process of toponymization with a second name [2:8-26]. In our opinion, this term is appropriately used because it captures the essence of the phenomenon of naming toponyms. In this place, toponyms are not formed by themselves, but arise in their structure due to the need to name topoobjects and under the influence of toponymization phenomenon in toponymy. A set of toponymic materials collected for conducting scientific research is available in our language and shows that words that are actively used in practice are divided into two groups:

1. Words that exist in the language, but are not chosen to name objects and are not loaded with toponymic meaning.

2. Lexical bases, i. e. , toponyms, selected due to the need to name objects and loaded with the subtlety of toponymic meaning(s).

Our main goal is to create a study of toponyms formed from the second group of words, that is, from the lexical bases that are selected due to the need to name objects and loaded with toponymic meanings. The word that forms the basis of a toponym, i. e. , the lexical base that motivates the formation of a name, differs from ordinary words in that it expresses certain toponymic meaning(s) due to the process of onomastic conversion. In nomenclature, in particular, in toponymy, the phenomenon of toponymization means that the lexical base, i. e. , appellatives (same words) are selected and in the process of naming, taking individual meaning(s) specific to objects (i. e. , specific to the topoobject) and moving to a toponym. Here, the natural conditions related to the topological objects motivate the formation of individual meanings of the selected words.

Formation of toponyms and word formation of appellative words are evaluated as one thing [4]: "Toponyms, including hydronyms, do not differ from word

formation in terms of the principle of formation. Word formation methods and word formation tools in each language are also involved in toponym formation. But when examining the names of places and water bodies from the point of view of word formation, it is necessary to take into account the specific semantic and grammatical features of proper nouns. In the first and second sentences, there is a sense of saying the same thing about word formation in grammar and word formation in onomastics. In the third sentence, it is said that toponyms have semantic and grammatical properties. That is, we are talking about similarities and certain differences. In order to avoid such duality, it was necessary to say that word formation in toponyms is different from word formation in grammar.

It is also known from research that toponyms, like other onomastic units, differ from ordinary (appellative) words by the following characteristics:

1. Words, more precisely, lexemes in an independent word group have a lexical meaning. Toponyms represent the names of separate, natural-geographical objects and have a defining feature, that is, a noun with a toponymic meaning. Here, the term toponymic meaning is used in an encyclopedic sense, meaning the nationality of the people who gave the name, showing geographical and ethnographic features. The reason is that there are no meaningless names in nature. If you come across such names, especially toponyms, know that they have not been specially researched from a scientific and practical point of view.

2. If words are the product of naming in a broad sense, toponyms formed from them are a type of nouns that are formed due to the phenomenon of toponymization and express toponymic meaning. For example, the syntactic unit "Qil chuvat ariq" is a sentence. Due to the phenomenon of toponymic derivation, it turned from a syntactic unit into a whole word and moved to a toponym: qil+chuv+-at +ariq * qili +chuvat ariq * qilchuvatariq * Kilchuvatariq (I. t. , Azamat MFY. Qirkyiyigit q. ariq) Or: Kampir+di'oldi*Kampiro'oldi (P. t. , Industrial MFY, q.).

It is clear from the above that words that are lexical units do not automatically become toponyms. For this, they should be selected as lexical bases from the system of appellative words, they should be motivated to acquire toponymic meanings, that is, they should be aimed at expressing the toponymic meaning, and should meet the normative requirements of the specialized lexicon of the language. In the context of this phenomenon, onomastic conversion and toponymic derivation processes apply.

In the process of toponymic derivation, which is the second form of the phenomenon of toponymization, there are two types of formation of words in the

appellative lexicon, creation of a new word, and their selective transfer to the level of the toponymic lexicon:

1) by adding a topoforment to a certain topoisos, a lexical base is created in the appellative lexicon and it moves to a toponym: *ena+–ng+ yaxshi* > *enang yaxshi* > *Enang yaxshi*; *xatir+- chi* > *xatirchi* > *Xatirchi* (Azamat MFY); *xon+jilg‘a+li* > *xonjig‘ali* > *Xonjig‘ali*; *jin+-li* > *jinli* > *Jinli* (I. t. , q.); *bir+-lik* > *birlik* > *Birlik* (I. t. , mahalla); *oy+tamg‘a+-li* > *Oytamg‘ali* (P. t. , Birlashgan MFY, q.), *baliq+-chi* > *Baliqchi* (P. t. , Ko‘kdala MFY, q.)

2) by adding two words (indicator to topoasos) chosen for naming, a new lexical base is created and it moves to the onomastic lexicon and becomes a name for the object: *oq +qo‘rg‘on* > *oqqo‘rg‘on* > *Oqqo‘rg‘on* (P. t. , Birlashgan MFY, q.); *o‘rta+ovul* > *o‘rta ovul* > *o‘rtaovul* > *O‘rtaovul*; *mirza+ovul* > *mirza ovul* > *Mirzaovul*; *tentak + ovul* > *tentak ovul* > *Tentakovul*; *turkman+ovul* > *turkman ovul* > *Turkmanovul* (P. t. , O‘rtato‘sin MFY, q.). It is clear from this that the phenomenon of toponymization means that the lexical bases of toponyms have moved to the level of toponymic lexicon. The motivation of toponyms occurs as a result of connection of the event of toponymization with the processes of onomastic conversion and toponymic derivation. It takes into account the transformation of lexical bases into an onomastic lexicon, that is, a toponym.

So, this phenomenon serves to show the different and similar features of toponyms with related words more clearly. This phenomenon is considered a natural law that justifies the naming of objects. If there are objects, then it is named because of natural and social necessity. Naming confirms the existence of the event of toponymization.

The role and importance of the phenomenon of toponymization in the interpretation of the term toponymy in toponymy is extremely high. The reason is that the manifestations of the phenomenon of toponymization, such as onomastic conversion and toponymic derivation, also justify the diversity of the formation of toponyms.

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